

Table 1. Effect of C:N ratio and preflooding on panicle number and rice yield.^a Guangzhou, China, 1988.

C:N ratio	Panicle no.	Dry matter (g/pot)	
		Straw	Panicle
<i>Preflooded 2 wk</i>			
0	31 a	63 b	33
10	28 b	65 ab	29
25	23 c	45 c	29
40	9 d	16 d	3
<i>Preflooded 4 wk</i>			
0	29 ab	72 a	21
10	25 c	63 b	22
25	24 c	51 c	21
40	10 d	16 d	6
<i>Preflooded 6 wk</i>			
0	31 a	67 ab	23
10	27 bc	61 b	23
25	23 c	45 c	28
40	10 d	15 d	10

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by DMRT, P = 0.05.

straw yield (Table 1). Significant differences in tiller number and straw yield occurred with C:N ratio treatments (Table 1, 2).

With a C:N ratio of 25, tillers were fewer than those with no added rice straw and with a C:N ratio of 10, but more than those with a C:N ratio of 40.

The panicle number at harvest and straw dry weight were significantly lower with increased C:N ratios (Table 1).

Table 2. Effect of C:N ratio on rice tiller number at 2-15 wk after transplanting.^a Guangzhou, China, 1988.

C:N ratio	Tillers ^b (no.)									
	3	4	5	6	7	9	11	13	15	
0	6.0 a	24.8 a	27.9 a	32.4 a	33.4 a	31.6 a	24.6 a	22.6 a	22.1 a	
10	5.7 a	24.3 a	28.8 a	31.4 a	31.4 a	29.8 a	20.8 b	18.7 b	17.2 b	
25	4.0 b	19.7 b	22.6 b	25.7 b	25.9 b	24.3 b	17.7 c	15.0 c	14.7 c	
40	0.3 c	2.2 c	1.8 c	2.9 c	2.9 c	2.8 c	1.7 d	1.8 d	1.9 d	

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by DMRT, P = 0.05. ^bNo tillers appeared at 2 wk after transplanting.

Crop management

Effect of cultural practice for semideep water rice on yield and net income

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Poor crop stands due to low seeding rates, poor germination under premature flooding, high seedling mortality, and inadequate and untimely fertilizer application result in low productivity of direct seeded rice grown in semideep water.

Effect of cultural practices on yield and net income at Ghagharaghat, U.P., India, 1988 and 1989 wet seasons.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		Gross income (\$/ha)		Total cost (US\$/ha)	Net income (\$/ha)		Net income/\$ invested	
	1988	1989	1988	1989		1988	1989	1988	1989
FPOF	1.2	1.4	154	178	134	20	44	0.15	0.32
FPWF	1.5	2.0	193	257	162	31	95	0.19	0.58
DSNS	2.4	2.9	309	377	168	141	209	0.84	1.24
DSES	2.8	3.4	360	436	181	179	255	0.99	1.40
DSPI	2.1	2.3	263	292	193	70	99	0.36	0.51
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aFPOF = farmer's practices without fertilizer (direct sown with onset of monsoon) - check. FPWF = farmer's practices with fertilizer (40 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha) - direct sown at onset of monsoon. DSNS = direct sown with normal seeding rate (100 kg/ha) and 40 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha in well-prepared field before onset of monsoon. DSES = direct sown with 150 kg seed/ha + 40 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha in well-prepared field before onset of monsoon. DSPI = dry sowing with 40 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha and presowing irrigation on 15 May; crop was grown with supplementary irrigation till onset of monsoon.

Panicle dry weight did not differ significantly among C:N 0, 10, and 25 treatments, but was much lower with C:N 40.

Adding large quantities of rice straw appeared to reduce the efficiency of applied N. Preflooding did not change this effect. At C:N ratios above 10, microorganisms and rice plants may compete for available N as organic materials decompose. ■

Effect of seedling age on growth and yield of T. aman rice

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We evaluated growth and yield of 30-, 40-, and 60-d-old seedlings of rice varieties BR11, BR22, BR23, and Nizersail during 1988 T. aman season at BRRI, Joydebpur. Test plots were transplanted 15 Sep.

Tiller and panicle numbers did not differ significantly with seedling age in BR11 and Nizersail (see table). In BR22, seedling age was inversely related to tiller and panicle numbers. With 60-d-old seedlings, BR23 had the lowest tiller number but the most panicles. Grain yield, however, was no higher than at other seedling ages, probably, because late tillers increased competition for nutrients.

All the varieties are photoperiod sensitive so days to flowering and maturity of the different seedlings were similar.

Grain yield was highest with 45-d-old seedlings of BR23.

Transplanting 30- to 60-d-old seedlings had no significant effect on grain yield of BR11, BR22, or Nizersail. These